

SOCIAL MEDIA UTILIZATION FOR HEALTH SERVICE AWARENESS AT PUNTI KAYU PRIMARY HEALTH CARE

Henni Febriawati^{1*}, Rama Raju², Riana Dewi³, Risky Meirinasari⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Al-Su'aibah College of Health Sciences, Palembang

*Correspondent : henni_febriawati@al-suaibah.ac.id

ABSTRACT

Social media usage is growing rapidly, making it easier for people to communicate and share content. Platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, and WhatsApp are increasingly being used, including for marketing activities. In July 2024, the number of global social media users reached 5.17 billion, or 63.7% of the global population. In Indonesia, internet users reached 185.3 million in January 2024, an increase of 1.5 million social media users compared to the previous year. The average Indonesian uses social media for 3 hours and 14 minutes per day, and 81% access it daily. In South Sumatra, social media users reached 70.54% of the total population in 2024, while in Palembang the figure was higher at 83.73%. To determine the relationship between age, gender, education, knowledge, and attitudes with the use of social media in increasing public awareness of health services. The study used a quantitative design with an analytical survey method and a cross-sectional approach. A total of 98 respondents were selected as a sample, with data collected through observation, interviews, and secondary data from community health center documents. Data were analyzed using a bivariate test with an Odds Ratio (OR) calculation. The results showed a significant relationship between age ($p=0.000$; $OR=47.308$), gender ($p=0.037$; $OR=0.366$), knowledge ($p=0.000$; $OR=6.364$), and attitude ($p=0.000$; $OR=33.065$) with social media use. Respondents who were young, female, well-informed, and had a positive attitude were more likely to use social media to access health information. Meanwhile, education did not have a significant relationship with social media use ($p=0.728$). The use of social media has been shown to be closely related to individual characteristics, especially age, knowledge, and attitudes.

Keywords : Social Media, Health Services, Community Health Centers

INTRODUCTION

The digital era is a time when the development of information technology is taking place very rapidly and influencing almost all aspects of people's lives, including the way people communicate, work, and obtain information. This digital transformation is increasingly evident with the presence of social media which allows the exchange of information to take place in a matter of seconds (1). This technological development has brought about major changes in people's information consumption patterns, who now rely more on gadgets and the internet than traditional media. Social media is not only a means of communication, but also a digital public space that allows the dissemination of information widely, quickly, and easily accessible to various groups. This condition creates a huge opportunity for various sectors, including health services, to utilize social media as a strategic information channel (2).

Social media, such as Instagram, TikTok, Facebook, and WhatsApp, are now dominant communication platforms in various countries. Their use allows them to reach a wide audience at

a lower cost than conventional promotional or outreach methods. By 2024, the number of global social media users is expected to reach 5.17 billion people, equivalent to 63.7% of the world's population, while in Indonesia the number will reach 185.3 million users. These high numbers indicate that social media has become part of people's daily lives. In fact, the average Indonesian spends more than three hours per day accessing social media, giving these platforms enormous potential for conveying information, including health information. Thus, social media is a relevant and effective medium for disseminating health messages that require broad reach and rapid interaction capabilities (3) .

In the healthcare sector, social media has undergone significant functional development, from being a mere promotional tool to a means of building relationships with the public. Social media enables healthcare facilities such as community health centers and hospitals to provide health education, answer patient questions, publish service schedules, convey disease-related information, and enhance a positive image through more open interactions. Previous research also shows that social media can increase patient trust and strengthen the reputation of healthcare services. This is important because trust is one of the main factors influencing people's decisions in choosing a healthcare facility. Therefore, social media is no longer merely considered a supplement, but has become an essential part of modern healthcare communication strategies (4) .

Furthermore, social media plays a significant role in raising public awareness of health issues. Through visual content such as infographics, educational videos, live streaming, and digital health campaigns, information can be presented in a more engaging and easily understood manner. Social media also enables two-way interaction between health workers and the public, allowing complaints and questions to be conveyed and acted upon quickly (5) . Furthermore, collaboration between health agencies, the government, and non-profit organizations is also increasingly facilitated through social media, particularly in disseminating information during public health issues such as disease outbreaks or disasters. Thus, this digital platform can improve public health literacy and help accelerate changes in health behavior toward the better (6) .

Despite its significant potential, the use of social media in healthcare services is not evenly distributed across regions, including the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center. Data shows that the number of followers on the community health center's Instagram and Facebook accounts is still significantly lower than the population in its area of operation. Initial observations indicate that some residents are unaware of the community health center's official account. Many use social media solely for entertainment or to follow viral news, resulting in less than optimal dissemination of health information from the community health center. This indicates a gap between the potential of social media as a health education tool and the level of utilization by the local community. Social media, however, has significant potential to help the community obtain information about doctor schedules, types of health services, disease information, and ongoing health programs (7) .

In addition to low utilization, public knowledge and attitudes towards the use of social media as a source of health information also influence their level of awareness of community health center services. Some people may not be accustomed to obtaining health information from social

media, while others are not yet aware that information provided by community health centers can help them in making decisions regarding the necessary health services (8) . Therefore, it is important to know the level of public knowledge and attitudes regarding the use of social media in the context of health services. This information is needed to understand the factors influencing low public awareness so that more targeted and effective digital communication strategies can be designed.

Based on this phenomenon, research on the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center in 2025 is important to conduct. This study aims to describe community characteristics, identify the relationship between knowledge and attitudes with social media utilization, and assess the extent to which social media plays a role in increasing awareness of health services at the community health center. The results of this study are expected to provide benefits to educational institutions as reference material, to the community health center as input in improving the quality of social media-based services, and to future researchers as a basis for developing research related to health communication and the use of digital media. With a better understanding of the role of social media, the community health center can improve its communication strategy so that health information can be conveyed more effectively and have an impact on the community.

METHODS

This study used a quantitative design with an analytical survey and a cross-sectional approach, namely data was collected once to see the relationship between knowledge and attitudes with the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center (9) . The study population was all patients who visited in February–April 2025, totaling 4,135 patients. The sample was calculated using the Slovin formula (1% error) and obtained 98 respondents. The sampling technique used accidental sampling, namely respondents who were met directly at the Community Health Center and met the inclusion criteria.

Data were collected using a questionnaire that had been tested for validity on 30 respondents, and all items were declared valid. The dependent variable was the role of social media, while the independent variables were knowledge and attitude. Knowledge was categorized as good if the score was $>75\%$, attitude was good if the score was $>\text{median } 10$, and the role of social media was categorized as beneficial if the score was ≥ 29 . Primary data came from respondents and secondary data from Community Health Center documents. The study was conducted in accordance with ethical principles of health research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Result

Univariate analysis is used to describe each variable studied in the research, namely by looking at the frequency distribution of independent and dependent variables presented descriptively.

Table 1
Frequency distribution of respondent characteristics at Pundi Kayu Health Center, Palembang

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age		
Young <35 Years	31	31.6
Age ≥35 years	67	68.4
Gender		
Man	32	32.7
Woman	66	67.3
Education		
High >D3-S3	16	16.3
Low ≤SMA	82	83.7
Knowledge		
Good	71	72.4
Not good	27	27.6
Attitude		
Good	26	26.5
Not good	72	73.5
The Role of Social Media		
Utilise	56	57.1
Not Taking Advantage	42	42.9
Total	98	100.0

The results of the frequency distribution of respondents' ages from 98 respondents who are in the old category are 67 (68.4%) respondents, more than the respondents in the young category 31 (31.6%) respondents. Of the 98 respondents who are female, 66 (67.3%) respondents are more than the respondents who are male, 32 (32.7%) respondents. Of the 98 respondents who have low education, 82 (83.7%) respondents are more than the respondents who have high education, 16 (16.3%) respondents. Of the 98 respondents who are good at knowing, there are 71 (72.4%) respondents, more than the respondents who are not good at knowing, there are 27 (27.5%). Of the 98 respondents who are not good, there are 72 (73.5%) respondents, more than the respondents who are good, there are 26 (26.5%). Of the 98 respondents, the role of the media that does not utilize 56 (57.1%) respondents is more than the respondents who utilize 42 (42.9%).

The relationship between age, gender, education and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center in 2025

The results of the bivariate analysis between age, gender, education and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center are as shown in Table 2.

Table 2

The relationship between age, gender, and education with the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center in 2025

Variable	The Role of Social Media				Total		<i>P Value</i>
	Utilise		Not taking advantage of		N	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Age							
Young <35 Years	30	96.8	1	3.2	31	100	0,000
Age ≥35 years	26	38.8	41	61	67	100	
Gender							
Man	13	40.6	19	59.4	32	100	0.037
Woman	43	57.1	23	34.8	66	100	
Education							
Height >D3-S3	8	50.0	8	50.0	16	100	0.728
Low ≤SMA	48	58.5	34	41.5	82	100	
Amount	56	57.1	42	42.9	98	100	

The results of the bivariate test showed a significant relationship between age and the role of social media ($p\text{-value} = 0.000$; OR = 47.308) indicating that respondents in the younger age category were 47.308 times more likely to use social media than older respondents. This means that young people are more likely to learn about technological developments and are more active in seeking health information through social media.

Bivariate test results showed a significant relationship between gender and the role of social media ($p\text{-value} = 0.037$; OR = 0.366), indicating that male respondents were 0.366 times less likely to use social media than female respondents. This means that women are significantly more likely to use social media to obtain health information and services.

Bivariate test results showed no significant relationship between education level and the role of social media ($p\text{-value} = 0.728$). This means that respondents with high and low education levels have a relatively equal opportunity to utilize social media for health services.

The relationship between knowledge and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center in 2025.

The results of the bivariate analysis between knowledge and the role of social media variables in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center are as shown in Table 3.

Table 3

The relationship between knowledge and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center in 2025

Knowledge	The role of social media				Total		<i>P</i> <i>value</i> 0,000
	Utilise		Not taking advantage of		N	%	
	n	%	n	%	N	%	
Good	49	69.0	22	31.0	71	100	
Not good	7	25.9	20	74.1	27	100	
Amount	56	57.1	42	42.9	98	100	

Based on table 3, the results obtained from 71 respondents who utilized more were well-informed, namely 49 (69.0%) compared to 7 (25.9%) who were not well-informed, while from 27 respondents who did not utilize the role of social media, there were 22 (31.4%) who were well-informed, compared to 20 (74.1%) who were not well-informed. Based on the results of statistical tests, a *p* value of 0.000 < 0.05 was obtained. This means that there is a significant relationship between knowledge and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Health Center. From the results of the analysis, an OR value of 6.364 was obtained, meaning that good knowledge has a 6.364 times higher risk of utilizing the role of social media compared to those who do not have good knowledge.

The relationship between attitudes and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center in 2025.

The results of the bivariate analysis between the attitude variable and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center are as shown in Table 4.

Table 4

The relationship between attitudes and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center in 2025

Attitude	The role of social media				Total		<i>P</i> <i>value</i> 0,000
	Utilise		Not taking advantage of		N	%	
	n	%	n	%	N	%	
Good	25	96.2	1	3.8	36	100	
Not good	31	43.1	41	56.9	62	100	
Amount	56	57.1	42	42.9	98	100	

Based on table 4, the results obtained from 36 respondents who utilized more had bad attitudes of 31 (43.1%) compared to good 25 (43.1%) while from 62 respondents who did not

utilize the role of social media, there were more bad attitudes of 41 (56.9%) compared to good attitudes of 1 (3.8%) based on the results of statistical tests obtained p value = 0.000 < 0.05 this means that there is a significant relationship between attitudes and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Health Center in 2025 from the results of the analysis also obtained an OR value = 33.065 meaning that good attitudes have a 33.065 times higher risk of utilizing the role of social media compared to those who do not have good attitudes.

Discussion

The relationship between age, gender, education and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center in 2025

“Young” respondents were 47.3 times more likely to use social media for health than older respondents (OR = 47.308; p = 0.000). This indicates that young age is strongly correlated with social media utilization. Younger respondents are much more likely to use social media to obtain health information/services in line with the literature showing much higher penetration and use of social media in the productive age group/young adults, so they are more likely to adopt online platform-based health information for various health purposes (information search, peer support, health behavior reminders) (10). This is consistent with the understanding that the younger generation is more adaptive to digital technology, more digital media literate, and more actively seeks online information, including health information. Students as a productive age group/young, use social media (Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, Facebook) intensively to seek health information and that this social media has an important role in increasing awareness of healthy lifestyles. Community health center health programs that utilize social media (e.g., Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp, TikTok) are likely to be effective in reaching and increasing awareness of younger groups, but require special strategies to reach older age groups (e.g., digital literacy training, a combination of traditional and digital media) (11)

A significant influence of gender was identified, with women more likely to use social media for health related purposes than men (OR = 0.366; p = 0.037). This reflects differences in gender roles in health information-seeking behavior, with women more often taking the initiative to seek health information or being more open to receiving health information on social media. Women tend to use social media for health information/services more intensively, which can be explained by gender role patterns in seeking health information (women are often the “decision makers” regarding family/child health and tend to be more proactive in seeking information). Although not all studies specifically compare genders, research and reviews on the “role of social and traditional media in health promotion” often show that traditional media such as posters and social media are effective in reaching vulnerable or active groups in public health, and these groups are often at risk or require more intensive health information (e.g., adolescents, women, mothers) that is “easy to remember, read, and easy to post anywhere” (12).(13)

The research results showed that good health knowledge was significantly correlated with social media use (OR: 6.364; p = 0.000), and a positive attitude significantly increased the

probability of social media use (OR: 33.065; $p = 0.000$). Cognitive (knowledge) and affective (attitude) aspects of health significantly influence whether someone uses social media for health information/services. People with positive knowledge and attitudes towards health are more likely to use social media to raise awareness or seek health services. This is in line with research that shows social media allows for wide-reaching, interactive information dissemination, but also emphasizes the importance of content consistency and credibility for information to be accepted.(14) .

In contrast, no significant relationship was found between education level and social media use ($p = 0.728$). This means that both respondents with high and low education had relatively equal opportunities. Formal literacy (education) does not always correlate with digital literacy or interest in using social media for health. Social media use may be more influenced by access, motivation, digital habits, and the need for health information not just educational background. Many studies have shown that “access to social media” and “active/passive engagement” as well as interesting and relevant content are more important determinants of the success of social media as a health education tool than demographic factors such as education. Social media increases public health awareness because it allows for the rapid and interactive dissemination of information, regardless of specific demographic backgrounds (14).

The relationship between knowledge and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center in 2025

The results of the bivariate test showed a significant relationship between knowledge and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center, with a value (p -value = 0.000; OR = 6.364). This means that respondents who have good knowledge are 6.364 times more likely to use social media than respondents with poor knowledge. This study also found that there were respondents who had good knowledge but did not use social media for health, this happened due to other factors beyond knowledge, such as limited internet access and lack of information on official Puskesmas accounts. Conversely, there were also respondents with poor knowledge who still used social media, possibly due to family or friend factors.

Knowledge is the process of someone's 'knowing' that occurs after sensing or intervening in something (15) . Good knowledge can influence attitudes and behavior. Good knowledge will make someone tend to have a positive attitude to take preventative measures and if a positive attitude has been formed, it will also give rise to good behavior. Knowledge is very necessary to shape someone's behavior. Knowledge influences or is correlated with risk perception, where the higher the knowledge, the lower the risk perception (16) .

This research is in line with the research conducted (17) based on the results of statistical test data using *the Paired T-Test* with the help of SPSS, calculations were carried out to determine whether there was an influence on the level of use of social media as a medium with the level of knowledge of adolescent reproductive health. The results of the p value calculation were $0.000 < \alpha$ (0.05). If the p value $< \alpha$ (0.05) means there is an influence of the use of social media as a health

promotion medium on the level of knowledge of adolescent reproductive health at SMPN 1 Sakra, this shows that 0.000 is smaller than 0.05. Thus, H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected.

Based on the results of the study, theories, and related research, the researcher assumes that there is a relationship between knowledge and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at Community Health Centers (Puskesmas). This is because the higher a person's knowledge, the easier it is for them to understand and respond to health information disseminated through social media. Good knowledge makes people more interested and active in following service information, thus increasing their awareness of the importance of utilizing Puskesmas services.

The relationship between attitudes and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center in 2025

The results of the bivariate test showed that there was a significant relationship between attitudes and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center, with a value ($p\text{-value} = 0.000$; $OR = 33.065$) meaning that respondents who had good attitudes were 33.065 times more likely to utilize social media than respondents who had bad attitudes. This study also found that there were some respondents who had good attitudes but did not utilize social media due to factors such as limited internet access, not knowing the official account of the Community Health Center, on the other hand, there were also respondents who had bad attitudes but still utilized social media. This may have happened because they were exposed to health information accidentally when using social media.

Attitude is a reaction or response that is still closed from a person to a stimulus or object (Angraini et al., 2024). An individual is very closely related to each attitude as one of his personal characteristics. Attitude in general can be interpreted as an action that a person takes towards something. *Attitude* is defined as a learned tendency to respond in a pleasant or unpleasant way consistently regarding a particular object. (19)

This research is in line with the research conducted (20) based on the results of the t-test, a significant p value of 0.030 was obtained or $p < 0.05$, so H_o was rejected, meaning there was a relationship between attitudes and leptospirosis prevention behavior in the city of Bima, West Nusa Tenggara.

Based on the results of theoretical and related research, the researcher assumes that there is a relationship between attitudes and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services at Community Health Centers (Puskesmas). Positive attitudes make people more open, receptive, and put health information obtained from social media into practice. Positive attitudes encourage people to respond to information with concrete actions, thus increasing awareness of the importance of utilizing Puskesmas services.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results and discussion, this study concluded that of the 98 respondents, the majority were in the older age group (67 respondents) (68.4%), female (66 respondents) (67.3%), and most had low education levels (82 respondents) (83.7%). In addition, 71 respondents (72.4%)

had good knowledge, 72 respondents (73.5%) had bad attitudes, and 56 respondents (67.1%) used social media to increase awareness of health services. This study also found a significant relationship between knowledge and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services, indicated by a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, there was a significant relationship between attitudes and the role of social media in increasing public awareness of health services, with a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author would like to thank all parties who contributed to the completion of this research. The author extends his deepest appreciation to **the Pundi Kayu Community Health Center in Palembang** for their permission and support throughout the research process, as well as to all **respondents** who took the time to provide the required data.

The author also thanks colleagues who assisted in data collection, analysis, and refinement of this manuscript. All contributions and assistance were invaluable to the completion of this research.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST AND FUNDING DISCLOSURE

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in the writing of this article. This research did not receive any specific funding from any party .

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

HF (Henni Febriawati): data curation, investigation, validation, project administration: RRJ (Rama Raju): concept, methodology, formal analysis, supervision, writing review & editing; RD (Riana Dewi): visualization, resources, writing original draft; RM (Risky Meirinasari): writing original draft, writing review & editing.

REFERENCES

1. Sinulingga SPB, Nasution MIP. Analysis of Challenges and Opportunities in the Development of Information and Communication Technology in the Digital Era: Future Perspectives. *J Ilm Ekon dan Manaj.* 2024;2(12):25–35.
2. Fauzan M, Purwanto E, Jupri HDN, Dewi PS. Media as an Agent of Community Change in the Digital Technology Era. *J Bisnis dan Commun Digit.* 2025;2(4):1–15.
3. Erwin, Judijanto L, Yuliasih M, Nugroho MA, Amien Neneng N, Mauliansyah F. *Social Media Marketing Trends.* Jambi: PT. Sonpedia Publishing Indonesia; 2023.
4. Saimi. *Smart Health Promotion: The Era of Globalization and Digital Transformation.* Central Java: Arta Media Nusantara Publisher; 2025.
5. P FPA, Darman LP, Clarisa M. The Role of Social Media Instagram @kemenkes_ri in M. *Titian J Hum.* 2024;08(02).
6. Sentanu IGEPS, Yustiari SH. *Managing Stakeholder Collaboration in Public Services.* Jakarta: PT Indonesia Delapan Kreasi Nusa; 2024.

7. Tsabita R, Sugandi MS. Analysis of Satisfaction Gap in the Utilization of Health Service Websites in Indonesia. *J Commun Sci.* 2021;19(3):321–40.
8. Arayana AR, Damayanti IA, Zakki MH, Salisah NH. Decision Analysis and Understanding of Consumer Behavior in a Health Communication Perspective. *Media and Commun Conf.* 2024;1(1):20–9.
9. Rahmadini S, Ernawaty. The Use of Social Media as a Marketing Tool for Adolescent Reproductive Health Awareness. *J Public Health.* 2024;12(3):274–87.
10. Chen J, Wang Y, Chen J. Social Media Use for Health Purposes : Systematic Review Corresponding Author : *J Medicinal Internet Res.* 2021;23(5):1–16.
11. Suryanti R, Villia AS, Sari AZC. The Effectiveness of Social Media on Students' Awareness of Healthy Lifestyles. *Khatulistiwa J Educators and Sos Hum.* 2025;5(3).
12. Pribody SP, Solihin O. The Role of Social Media in Increasing the Effectiveness of Health Promotion in Generation Z. *Al-Kaff J Sos Hum.* 2024;2(4):1–8.
13. Febriawati H, Efrianti D, Yanuarti R, Oktarianita, Angraini W. Poster Development as a Promotional Media for COVID-19 Prevention. *J Kesmas Asclepius.* 2022;4(2):42–51.
14. Rahmadini IM, Ayuningtyas D, Sulistiadi W. Utilization of Social Media to Increase Hospital Brand Awareness: Literature Review. *J Kesehat Tambusai.* 2025;6(1):596–602.
15. Wulan Angraini. HEALTH EDUCATION ON STUNTING IN NORTH BENGKULU DISTRICT Health Education Stunting in North Bengkulu Wulan Angraini *, Bintang Agustina Pratiwi , M . Amin , Riska Yanuarti , Henni Febriawati , M . Ismail Shaleh Public Health Study Program Faculty II. 2020;14(1):30–6.
16. Pratiwi BA, Fidella A, Oktavidiati E, Oktarianita O, Febriawati H. Factors Associated with COVID-19 Prevention Behavior in College Students. *J Public Health Sciences.* 2022;11(02):137–43.
17. Herli Masturi, Husniyati Sajalia, R Supini. The Influence of Using Social Media as a Health Promotion Media on the Level of Reproductive Health Knowledge of Adolescents at SMPN 1 Sakra. *ProHealth J.* 2023;20(2):47–52.
18. Angraini W, Febriawati H, Yanuarti R, Fatmawati T, Rizal AF. The Effectiveness of Educational Media Videos and Leaflets on Knowledge and Attitudes About Waste Management at State Senior High School 11, Bengkulu City. *J Nurs Public Heal.* 2024;12(1):115–21.
19. And S, Student P, Using D, Kurniawan D. SOCIAL AS A SUPPORTING TOOL FOR STUDENT LECTURES OF THE FACULTY OF ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS, UNIVERSITY OF JAMBI (FEB UNJA) Social Media as a Supporting Tool. 2022;2(April).
20. DI City, NTB B. *Jurnal Delima Harapan 2020* *Jurnal Delima Harapan 2020.* 2020;7:24–30.